

The Teacher's Perception of the Influence of Conditions of Service on their Productivity Secondary School in Central Senatorial District Kogi State

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Abstract:- This study investigated the teacher's perception of the influence of conditions of service on their productivity. Secondary school in central senatorial district Kogi state. The data collected are two hundred teachers which were randomly selected in six zone of central senatorial district. A deceptive survey design was adopted for the study. Questionnaire (TPOCSOP-R=0776) used to collect data. The data were collected and analysed using both the descriptive statistics, Pearson movement coefficient and inferential statistics (t-test) five hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result shows that there is no significant difference between male and female teachers perception on the influence of conditions of service on their productivity. There is a significant relationship between teacher's years of experience and their perception on the influence of service on their productivity. There is no significant difference among teachers of various age brackets in their perception of the influences of conditions of service on their productivity. There is no significant difference of among teachers with different academic qualification in their perception of the influence of condition of service on their productivity. There is no significant difference among teachers of different subject specialization in their perception of the influence of condition of service on their productivity. The status of profession to some extent determines the degree of prestige, pride and commitment which the practitioner gives the profession. The condition of service also determines the extent of job satisfaction and motivation of the workers.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to God's command for man, Moses commanded the Israelite that they should work and not be idle, but set a time for them to rest after work. In support of human industry, Apostle Paul admonished the Thessalonians to labour and toil days and night so that would not be a burden to anybody (2 Thess 3:10) he further instructed that "if a man will not work, he should not eat" emphasis is placed on work because it is the only means that provide subsistence, individualistic achievement in which we can attain highly valued rewards like sends of worth, prestige, social status, enriching life experience and satisfaction. Also in (1 Tim: 5:18) the scripture says, you shall not muzzle the ox that treads out the corn. And the labour is worthy of his reward. Therefore, we can say that to work in other to earn our living is never a crime and teachers should not be an exception. In any society, the teaching profession is probably the largest single profession. It is however not the

most attractive, but it is definitely the profession that makes the greatest impact on the overall development of the society. Despite the relatively little recognition given to the teacher by the public, the teacher still 6 remains one of the most significant, even final determinates of the contours of most educational system. No nation shall be able to take its rightful place among nations without good teachers, it is the teachers who produce the manpower requirement of the nations by producing other professionals such as medical doctors, engineers, lawyers among others. However, the more existence of teachers is the existence of teachers in the educational system is not enough to guarantee the socio – economic development of the country if such teachers are not productive. It must be noted that Federal Government of Nigeria (1981:8) stated that 2the central objective of Nigeria is to produce a free, just and democratic society, a lad full opportunities for all citizens a great and dynamic economy and a united, strong and self – reliant nation". Joseph, (1988) argued that the teachers are the real architect of country's economic development as a meaning economic planning cannot take place if there is no educational and education cannot be if the teachers are not there. Teachers productivity is the degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which teacher prove qualitative education to the citizenry. Thus, the federal government of Nigeria (1981:18) clearly stated that "the purpose of teacher education is to produce highly 7 motivated and conscientious classroom teachers for all level of our educational system and to enhance their commitment to the nation objectives" however, it must be admitted that not all Nigeria teachers are highly productive because teachers are not highly motivated in support of this, the renowned theorist M.C Gregor observed that originally the average human being has an inherent dislike work and will avoid it if he can. In any organization each people are not merely a collection if individual, they perceive themselves as members of a group. This group recognized that interpersonal and group values were superior to individual values. Many theories have looked at those factors that make man to want to put in their best and have as well examined human behaviour and found out that it is not a simple matter, but should be looked at as system of variables. The interaction of human behaviour at work is definitely influence by certain factors which are important elements that enhance can be refers to as the conditions of service to motivate workers for higher productivity. Manpower development can occur in any organization, if the workers are been motivated by the government and train to become a good product to the Kogi state ministry of education Kogi State as a case in point. 8 In ministry of education Kogi State, workers received poor attention which led to brain – drain service to other

ministries. Therefore, this project assumes that poor conditions of service contribute to low productivity among teacher in Nigeria, particular in Kogi State.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Poor condition of service is known to affect worker productivity. Conditions of service in teaching are considered favourable enough to motivate teachers to productivity. Poor conditions of service generated frustration, job dissatisfaction and low productivity among teacher, poor pay packages, irregular promotion and excessive work load, inadequate transportation and accommodation facilities for the teachers affect their productivity, job insecurity, lack of medical services and insurance coverage are problems facing teacher's low productivity. For the above reasons, teachers are not productive as expected. This has in turn negatively affected pupils' academic performances. The researcher, therefore want to explore ways of developing the available manpower for greater efficiency.

A. Research Question

- Is there any significant different between male and female teachers perception in the influence of condition of service on their productivity?
- it there any significant difference among teachers of various years of experience in their perceptions on the influence of various years of services on their productivity?
- is there they significant difference between teachers with differently academic qualification in their service on their productivity?
- is there any significant difference between teachers with differently academic qualification in their perceptions of the influence of conditions of service of their productivity?
- is there any significant different between teachers different subject specialization in their perceptions of the influence of condition of service on their productivity?

B. Hypotheses

For the purpose of deterring the perceptions and views of the teachers in the selected primary schools. The following hypotheses were structured for testing.

- There is no significant difference between male and female teachers perception on the influence of conditions of service on their productivity.
- There is a significant difference among teacher of various years of experience in their perceptions on the influence of condition of service on their productivity.
- There is no significant difference among teacher of various age bracket in their perceptions on the influence of conditions of service on their productivity.
- There is no significant difference among teachers with different academic qualification in their perception of the influence of conditions of service on teachers productivity?
- There is no significant difference between subject specializations on their perception of influence of condition of service on their productivity.

C. Objectives of the Study

The purpose was to examines, the influence of conditions of service on the productivity, specifically, the objectives were

- To find out how, whether there is a significant difference between male and female teachers perception on the influence of condition of service on teacher's productivity.
- To find out how, whether there is a significant different among teachers of various years of experiences in their perceptions on the influence of condition of service in teacher's productivity..
- To find out how, whether there is a significant difference among teacher of different age bracket in their perceptions on the influence of condition of service on teacher's productivity
- To find out how, whether there is a significant difference among teacher's in area of discipline or teaching subject on the influence of condition of service productivity.
- To find out how, whether there is a significant difference among teacher's qualification on the influence of condition of service on teacher's productivity.

D. Significance of the Study

This study will enable teachers, pupils, community and the government to know what responsible for low productivity and how it negatively affect the academic performance of the pupils. It will make the government to look into improving the conditions of service of the teachers. It will also be of good assistance to future researchers who may want to catty out research work on this same topic. It will expose the functions of teachers to the community. It will help the government to know the effects of motivating teacher to enhance the best performance.

E. Definition of Terms

- Productivity: is the output resulting from a given resource in put at a given time
- Motivation: Is the energizing force that induces or compels and maintain behaviour.
- Job satisfaction: This is a personal felling of contentment or discontentment, the level of which depends on the quality of interaction between the individual and his or her environment. iv.
- Job: A paid regular employment
- Welfare: The good health, happiness, comfort of a person or group of people.
- Employee: A person who work for some body or for government in return for wages
- Efficiently: Refers to an input – output relationship that is maximum work achieved for a minimum input of energy or resources.
- Service performance of a duty of function
- Manpower: Mena human resources x. Incentive: Compensation aimed at increasing production or simulating process toward organization goals.

III. METHODOLOGY

Introduction This chapter deals with the methodology adopted and used in carry out the investigation. In this chapter, the researcher will provide research design through population and sampling procedures and sources of data and the method of analysis. The study Is a basic exploratory Investigation aimed at increasing the knowledge of the researcher and finding out the teachers Perception on the influence of conditions of services on teacher's productivity.

A. Research Design

The design of this study s descriptive expose survey each. This is because the study attempt to find out the effect of condition of services on teachers productivity in LGEA from the teacher view. And also the researcher did not set up a situation to be studied. According to Nwanko, (1982) the purpose of descriptive research is to describe systematically some factual qualities or characteristics of a given population, event or a population, event of area of interest as factually and accurately as possible to answer the questions asked by problem under investigation. The descriptive research has the characteristics of accumulating. 50 Data base that is solely descriptive. In this wise, it does not necessarily Seek or explain relationship, test hypothesis, make predictions or get at meanings and implications, although, some other research design aimed at achieving these powerful purpose may incorporate descriptive methods. The statement of Nwankko above is further buttressed by Isaac drawing from Van Dulen and Mayor when he observed that descriptive research is to collect detailed factual information that describes existing phenomena and justified current conditions and practice. The survey is a type in which respondent answer agreed or disagreed, strongly agreed and strong disagreed type of questions. It means at survey research comprise or structure questions that accurately and precisely explain the current situation on teacher's productivity in Okene LGEA of Kogi State.

B. Population

The population of this study will consist of teaching staff in Central Senatorial Primary and Secondary Schools, Kogi State. The total population of Teaching and Non Academic Teaching Staffs were Two Thousand, Four Hundred and Fifty (2,450), Teaching Staff were, One Thousand Nine Hundred and Seventy Eight (1,978), and non-teaching Staff Four Hundred and Seventy Two (472). 51 There were One Hundred and Thirty Four (134) Primary and Secondary Schools in Kogi Central. Primary school is Ninety Five (95), Secondary Schools were thirty Nine (39), and these scho0ols are classified into five (5) zones. They are zone A, zone B, zone C, zone D, zone E zone F.

C. Sample and Sampling Procedure

Stratified random sampling techniques will be Used in the Selection of teachers. The procedure was careful planned by properly considering the statement of problem and hypothesis. The respondents were randomly were randomly selected based on the zonal system by which the schools are classified. A total number of two hundred (200 teachers) were selected for the study. The numbers of teacher selected

from each zone the purpose of this study were tabulated as follows: Zones Zone A Zone B Zone C Zone D Zone E Zone F Number of Teachers 33 33 34 34 33 33 respectively.

D. Research Instrument

Most of data used for this study were collected through primary and secondary sources from selected staffs of primary and secondary schools in Kogi Central. 52 Another instruments use to elicit information from all the respondents were open interview and structured questionnaires. In constructing the questionnaires, the researcher made use of hypothesis, statement of problem and the related literature reviewed. The questions consist of twenty (20) statements. The first part contained the demographic data requires the respondent to give his or her personal data in term of sex, occupation, rank and qualifications. Then the school part contained questions that call for agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed. All these questions in part B cantered on the issue raided in the statement of the problems hypothesis and literature review.

E. Validity and Reliability of Instrument

As described by Amin, (2005) validity is the degree to which a test measure what it is supposed to measure. To ensure validity of research instrument. Pilot testing of copies of questionnaire was carried out in primary and secondary schools in Kogi centre of Kogi State. This helped to assess the language clarity, ability to tap information from respondents, acceptability in term of length and ethical consideration for client. Supervisor were requested to rate the instruments in order to discover the validity. In order to establish content validity, result from the ratings was computed using the following formula. 53 $CVI = \frac{\text{Number of items rated as relevant}}{\text{Total number of items in the question}}$ This result into a content validity index 66% meaning that the instrument was valid. This reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbachi Alpha because according to Amin, (2005) the refresher used the Cronbach Alpha coefficient in order to establish reliability. This was calculated $A = K (1 - \sum sd^2) / K - L \sum sd^2$ where a = alpha Coefficient k = number of items, \sum = summation, sd^2 = squared standard Deviation with each items and sd^2 = total standard deviation squared) the result was 776 meaning that instrument was consistent and therefore reliable.

F. Method of Data Analysis

A total of two – hundred (200) questionnaires were administered and expected to be retrieved back. All responses were carefully critically observed. Their results were in percentage and in tabulation. The people interviewed were made to answer some questions drawn from the statement of the problem and the hypothesis. 54 The statistical instrument like t – test and one way ANOVA was used to test the analyses of the study and the hypothesis to know whether were the null hypothesis are rejected or accepted.

IV. PRESENTATION OF RESULT

In this chapter the results of the result of the analyses or data are presented. The summary of major findings of the study and the discussion of the findings are also presented in this chapter.

Tables 1 to 5 show the results of the study.

V. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

- **Research Question one:** is there any significant difference between male and female teachers perception on the influence of condition of service on teachers productivity?
- **Hypothesis one:** There in no significant difference between male and female teachers perception of the influence of condition service on teachers productivity. The student zed t - test analysis was use tor research question was used for research question one/Hypothesis one. The result is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: t – test analysis of the difference between male and female teachers perception on the influence of condition of service n productivity.

Comparison Variable n X x S t-cal Sig. Level

Level Male 90 69.33 6.35 1.664 0.098 Ns Female 110 59.69 7.40 Ns = Not significant at 0.05 alpha level The computed t – value of 1.664 was significant at 0.098 levels as shown in table 1 above. Since 0.05 alpha levels is less than mean scores of perception of male and female teachers on the influence of condition of service on their productivity do not differ significantly. Thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected and it was concluded that teachers irrespective of their sex have similar perception about the influence of condition of service on teachers.

- **Research Questions Two**
Is there any significant relationship between teachers' years of experience and their perception of service on teacher's productivity? **Hypothesis Two** There is no significant relationship between teachers' years of experience and their perception of service on teachers' productivity. These research questions / hypotheses were analysed using the Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient procedure.
- **Table 2:** Pearson's product moment correlation analysis of the relationship between years of experience and teachers perception on the influence of condition of services on teachers' productivity. Comparison Variable n x s r Sig. conclusion Level Years of Exp. 200 18.31 6.98 0.366 0.000 Sig. Teachers' Perception 200 60.43 6.98 Table 2 above indication that the computed correlation coefficient of 0.036 was significant at the 0.000 significant levels. This significant level is less than the 0.05 alpha level. Thus it was the null hypotheses were rejected and it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between the teachers' years of experience and teacher perception on the influence of condition of service on their productivity.

- **Research Question Three**

Is there is any significant different among teachers of different age bracket in their perception on the influence of conditions of service on teachers productivity?

- **Hypotheses Three**

There is no significant difference among teacher of different age bracket in their perception on the influence of conditions of service on teachers' productivity. To analyse the research question hypotheses the one – way, ANOVA was used. The result of the analysis is presented in table 3 as follows:

- **Table 3:** one- way ANOVA of the difference in perception on the influence of condition of service on teachers' productivity among teachers of different age brackets.

ANOVA Summary Source ss df ms F Sig. Level
Between Groups 190.335 3 63.452 1.606 0.190 Within Group 7309.973 185 39.513 Total 7500.328 188
Descriptive Statistics: Age Bracket n x s 1 5 58.60 5.37 2. 72 59.42 6.17 3. 102 61.25 6.63 4. 10 58.60 2.46 Total 189 60.34 6.32 X not significant at 0.05 alpha level is significant at 0.190 level of 1.606 is significant at 0.190 level. Since 0.05 alpha level of signature is less than 0.190 level the null hypotheses was retained. It was thus concluded that teachers with difference age group do 59 not differ significantly on their perception on the influence of condition of service on their productivity. Table 3 shown the corrupted means and standard deviation of teacher perception as need.

- **Research Question Four**

Is there any significant difference among teachers of various qualification in their perception on the influence of condition of service on teacher's productivity?

- **Hypotheses Four**

There is no significant difference among teacher with various qualifications in their perception on the influence of condition of service on teachers' productivity. To analyse the relevant data on this research question / hypotheses, the one – way ANOVA was used. The result is presented in table 4.

- **Table 4:** one – way ANOVA of difference in perception on the influence of condition of services on teachers' productivity among teachers of different qualifications. 60 ANOVA Summary: Source ss df ms F Sig. Level Between Groups 208.638 3 69.546 1.440 0.232 Within Group 9418.789 195 48.301 Total 9627.427 198
Descriptive Statistics: Qualification n x s 1 6 57.67 4.72 2. 97 60.98 6.87 3. 76 60.53 7.86 4. 20 57.85 2.76 Total 199 60.39 6.97 X not significant at the 0.05 alpha levels table 4 presents the result of the analysis of the difference in perception among teachers of different qualification of influence of condition of service on teachers' productivity. The complete F – ratio of 1.440 is significant at 0.232. Since the alpha level of 0.05 is less than this significant level, the null hypothesis was not rejected. It was thus concluded that teacher's with different academic qualification do not differ significantly on their perception on the influence of condition of service on teacher's productivity: table 4 also shows the means scores of the option.

• Research Question Five

Is there any significant difference among teachers in their perception on the influences of condition of service on teacher's productivity based on their teaching subject or discipline?

• Hypothesis Five

There is no significant difference among teachers in their perception on the influence of conditions of service on teachers' productivity based on their teaching subject or discipline. To Analyse this research question hypothesis, the one – way ANOVA was employed to analyse the relevant data generated. The result of this analysis is presented in table is presented in table 5 following. Table 5: one – w ay ANOVA of differences in teachers perception on the influence of condition of service on their productivity based on specialization. 62 ANOVA Summary: Source ss df ms F Sig. Level Between Groups 11.389 2 5.695 0.116 0.891 Within Group 9673.631 197 49.105 Total 9685.02 199 Descriptive Statistics: Subject Area n x s Arts 71 60.62 8.33 Social Sc. 85 60.15 6.13 Science 44 60.66 6.21 Total 200 60.43 6.98 X not sig. at 0.05 alpha levels. Table 5 indicates that the computed F – ratio of 0.1169 is significantly at 0.891 level. The alpha level of signature of 0.05 is less that 0.891 significant level. The null hypothesis stated was thus retained. This means teachers do not differ significantly in their perception based on their discipline or specialization.

VI. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study made attempt to investigate Teachers Perception on the influence of condition of services on their productivity. Some research questions were raised and research hypotheses were also proposed on the basis of determination, this hypothesis was conclusive. For hypotheses one, analysis of data revealed that there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on the influence on their productivity. Gender differences in condition of service situations are important in determining individual to psychological condition of service and their ability to cope under such circumstances. However, finding of Yahaya (1996) found no significant difference in the levels of experienced by male and female teachers, irrespective of sex or exposed to similar working conditions and work activities: the finding of Stoyanova and (2002) was not in agreement with the finding which stated previous research has established differences in men's and woman's psychological response to condition of service situation on their level of teachers productivity and ability to cope. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on the influence of conditions of services on teachers' productivity.

The finding from hypotheses two (2) revealed that there is significant relationship between teacher years of experience and their perception on the influence of conditions of service on teachers productivity significant difference was observed between the difference level of teachers productivity. Thus mean that not all teachers experience the same type of conditions of services at any level they are not with a particular coping strategy. Thus find indicated that teachers of years of experience is a

measure of quality and their imperative in the achievement of students' academic performance because teachers productivity is the degree of effectiveness and efficiency produce qualitative education to the citizenry. Thus, support that experienced teachers need to be retained in school if higher productivity is to be obtained because learners achieved more forms these teachers. (1997) and sol icy (1995) which say a class room teachers experience is highlight the influence of background and challenge to recreating a bridge. It was concluded that there is a significant difference relationship between the teachers' years of experience and teachers' years of experience and teachers perception on the influence of condition of service on their productivity. Finding from the hypothesis three revealed that no significant difference among teachers of various age brackets in their 66 perception of the influence of conditions of service on their productivity. The find support that could (1993) which showed no significant between subjects with different age. Finding of Dantan, (2000) disagreed with finding that there is significant difference among the group in the influence of conditions of services on teachers productivity. Thus study show that teachers under the study adopted a similar in dealing with various internal and external challenge of irrespective of their age. Thus finding is in line with pflastarer, (2004) who lighted that most of teachers had significant higher productivity as compare to the older teachers. However, Carloyn, (1990) revealed that there were no age differences in teachers' perception on the influence of condition of service on the teachers productivity. One interpretation of these results was that the nature of condition of service changes ages thus finding also disagreed with Danne, (2007) that males and female teacher influence by the condition of service, Reason that could be given for the finding includes the fact that the study result found people under 30 years old to be very productive. It was concluded that there is no significant different among teachers of different age group in their perception on the condition of services of their productivity.

The finding from hypothesis four (4) reveals that there is no significant difference among teachers with various academic qualifications in their perception on the condition of service on teachers' productivity. The find indicated that the majority of the teachers in their sample schools at the time of study were Bachelor of Science (Bsc), National certificate of Education (N.C.E) holder. This shows that Kogi State teaching personnel had followed the accordance ESG report of 2000 that state, majority of teachers in Nigeria primary school should be degree holder, this however call for putting in place necessary for these teachers to prepare to handle teaching and learning more effectiveness in the state primary school. This finding confirms Hammond, (2000) Egugun, 1993 and Iyamu, (2005) assertion that qualitative Education is a function of quality of teaching personnel within system. The finding point out that "No Education system can rise above the quality of teachers in the system" as stated in the National Policy of Education (FGN 2000). Finding strongly evidence that the condition work matter to teachers. They are important predictors of teacher productivity and their career intention even when holding constant the demographic

makeup school, in fact condition of Work explain a substantially 68 greater proportion of the variances in teacher productivity and career plans than student demographic characteristics. Not surprisingly individual teachers perception of working condition is strongly related to their satisfaction. Hypothesis five (5) the analysis of data revealed that no significant a difference was observed between subject specializations in term of influence of conditions of service on teachers productive. This means that all subject specialization, the same type of condition of services at any level they are and not with a particular influence on the condition of services. Thus result support Hubbaro, (2002) according to which everyone see situation differently and has different way of applying the condition of service for the betterment of their service of their student at given time, does not simply that it will be available for the same person to the extent at other times. Thus means teachers do not differ signature in their perception base on their discipline or specialization.

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